

Features

Challenge 0

“Which artwork will be added to the game?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 1

“Which feature can we use to attract players?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 2

“What can we implement to bring in more players?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 3

“How can we make the game more profitable?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 4

“What can we insert to keep players interested?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 5

“What feature can keep players engaged as difficulty increases?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 6

“How can we get players to take a break?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 7

“What feature can we use to optimize resource use?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 8

“What can we implement to ensure strong profit?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 9

“How can we insert to motivate players through rewards?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 10

“What can we use to keep players engaged as difficulty rises?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 11

“Which feature keeps players interested for a long-term?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

Challenge 12

“What feature can we use to keep the game profitable long-term?”

Red: Cell Fantasy (RPG Game)

Blue: Overcell (FPS Game)

Green: Cell Soccer (Sports Game)

